

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D8.6

XROTOR Design Review Report

<https://xrotor-project.eu>

@XROTORProject

April 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007135

Document Information

Deliverable ID	8.6
Deliverable Title	XROTOR Design Review Report
Lead beneficiary	University of Strathclyde
Contributing beneficiaries	
Due date Annex I	2024.04.30
Issue date	2024.04.30
Dissemination level	Public / Confidential
Author(s)	James Carroll (University of Strathclyde)

Approval

Version	Date	Description	Reviewed by	Approved by
1	2024/04/30		William Leithead and James Carroll <i>With 8 text James Carroll</i>	James Carroll <i>James Carroll</i>

Copyright

© 2022 X-ROTOR Consortium

The X-Rotor Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101007135. For more information on the project, its partners, and contributors please see <https://xrotor-project.eu>.

Disclaimer

The information contained in this document represents the views of X-ROTOR consortium as of the date they are published. The X-ROTOR consortium does not guarantee that any information contained herein is error-free, or up to date, nor makes warranties, express, implied, or statutory, by publishing this document. The information in this document is provided as is and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Commission nor its executive agencies are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

X-ROTOR Consortium

University of Strathclyde

Delft University of Technology

University College Cork – National University of Ireland, Cork

Fundacion Cener

General Electric Renovables España

Norwegian University of Science and Technology

CENER

NTNU – Trondheim
Norwegian University of
Science and Technology

UCC
Coláiste na hOllscoile Corcaigh, Éire
University College Cork, Ireland

<https://xrotor-project.eu>

Table of Contents

About X-ROTOR.....	5
1 Introduction/Description of the deliverable and its purpose.....	6
2 Annual Meeting 1.....	8
2.1 Annual Meeting 1 Overview	8
2.2 Annual Meeting 1 Agenda	8
2.3 Annual Meeting 1 Participants	9
3 Annual Meeting 2.....	9
3.1 Annual Meeting 2 Overview	10
3.2 Annual Meeting 2 Agenda	10
3.3 Annual Meeting 2 Participants	11
4 Annual Meeting 3.....	11
4.1 Annual Meeting 3 Overview	11
4.2 Annual Meeting 3 Agenda	12
4.3 Annual Meeting 3 Participants	12
5 Conclusions.....	13

About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

1 Introduction/Description of the deliverable and its purpose

Annual report on X-Rotor project and design review progress. This deliverable will be considered successfully complete when the report is made available to the Executive Management Group members or on the project website.

List of acronyms

VAWT	Vertical Axis Wind Turbine
HAWT	Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine
PMSG	Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator
UCC	University College Cork
UoS	University of Strathclyde
TU Delft	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
CENER	National Renewable Energy Centre
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
GE	General Electric

2 Annual Meeting 1

Thursday, 22 September 2022

GE Offices, Barcelona & virtually on MS Teams

2.1 Annual Meeting 1 Overview

The first workshop was hosted by GE at their offices in Barcelona. Each work package leader, supported by work package researchers, detailed the progress of their technical work, highlighting the technical challenges they face, the solutions they proposed and gave an overview of their next steps. Feedback was provided by GE attendees during the meeting, after the meeting at an evening event, following the meeting in emails/calls and through the GE lead at Technical Management Meetings (TMTs).

2.2 Annual Meeting 1 Agenda

Item	Time	Topic	Who
	09.00	Refreshment and welcome	
1.	09.15	PO update - Finance - Deliverables - Progress update – all WP's	UoS BL
	10.15	Comfort break	
2.	10.30	Work Package 7 presentation: Environmental and Socio-Economic Impact	UCC
3.	11.00	Work Package 9 presentation: Communication, Dissemination	UCC
4.	11.30	Discussion	
5.	11.45	Introduction to concept of X-ROTOR	UoS BL
6.	12.00	Work Package 6 presentation: Cost of Energy Reduction Analysis	UoS JC
	12.15	Break for lunch	
7.	13.15	Work Package 2 presentation: Aero-elastic code development and performance	TU Delft/CENER CSF / BLM
8.	14.00	Work Package 3 presentation: Control and Operational Strategy	UoS BL / LM
	14.45	Comfort break	
9.	15.00	Work Package 4 presentation: Design of mechanical structure & analysis	NTNU MM / ACS
10.	15.45	Work Package 5 presentation: Power take off and conversion system design	UoS OAL / DCG

11.	16.30	Discussion	
	17.00	Close meeting	BL

2.3 Annual Meeting 1 Participants

In person	
Jordi Jove-Bellot	GE
Kevin Cabeza	GE
Ramon Pinana	GE
Julien Pouilly	GE
Bill Leithead	UoS
James Carroll	UoS
Olimpo Anaya-Lara	UoS
David Campos-Gaona	UoS
Laurie Morgan	UoS
Nicola Baxter	UoS
Beatrix Méndez	CENER
Aurelio Cascales	CENER
Simon Watson	TU Delft
Michael Muskulus	NTNU
Adriana Correia da Silva	NTNU
Peter Deeney	UCC
Luke Smith	UCC
Ger Mullally	UCC

Online	
Mauricio Richter-Rios	EC Europa
Carlos Simao Ferreira	TU Delft
Yan Wu	TU Delft
Grant Allan	UoS
Peter Jamieson	UoS
Adam Stock	UoS

3 Annual Meeting 2

Tuesday 27th June 2023

Hotel Salles Pere IV, Barcelona & virtually on MS Teams

3.1 Annual Meeting 2 Overview

The second workshop was hosted near the GE offices in Barcelona. Each work package leader, supported by work package researchers, detailed the progress of their technical work, highlighting the technical challenges they face, the solutions they proposed and gave an overview of their next steps. Feedback was provided by GE attendees during the meeting, after the meeting at an evening event, following the meeting in emails/calls and through the GE lead at Technical Management Meetings (TMTs).

3.2 Annual Meeting 2 Agenda

Item	Time	Topic	Who
	09.15	Refreshment and welcome	
1.	09.30	Work Package 1: Project Management Deliverables	UoS JC
2.	09.45	Work Package 2: Aero-elastic code development and performance	TU Delft CS
3.	10.15	Work Package 3: Control and Operational Strategy	UoS BL
	10.45	Comfort / coffee break	
4.	11.00	Work Package 4: Design of mechanical structure & analysis	NTNU MM
5.	11.30	Work Package 5: Power take off and conversion system design	UoS DC-G / OAL
6.	12.00	Work Package 6: Cost of Energy Reduction Analysis	UoS / UCC JC / FMc
7.	12.30	Discussion	
	13.00	Break for lunch – 1 hour	BL / JJB
8.	14.00	Work Package 7: Environmental and Socio-Economic Impact	UCC ND
9.	14.30	Work Package 8: Industry Ratification and Further Development Roadmap	UoS BL
	15.00	Comfort / coffee break	
10.	15.15	Work Package 9: Communication, Dissemination	UCC ND
11.	15.45	Project-wide discussion Future plans	BL / JJB
	16.15	Close meeting	BL

3.3 Annual Meeting 2 Participants

In person	
Jordi Jove-Bellot	GE
Marc Guadayol	GE
Ramon Pinana	GE
Bill Leithead	UoS
James Carroll	UoS
Olimpo Anaya-Lara	UoS
David Campos-Gaona	UoS
Laurie Morgan	UoS
Nicola Baxter	UoS
Carlos Simao Ferreira	TU Delft
Michael Muskulus	NTNU
Adriana Correia da Silva	NTNU
Peter Deeney	UCC
Luke Smith	UCC

Online	
Simon Watson	TU Delft
Grant Allan	UoS
Peter Jamieson	UoS

4 Annual Meeting 3

Wednesday 20th March 2024
Bilbao Exhibition Centre & virtually on MS Teams

4.1 Annual Meeting 3 Overview

The final workshop was hosted at the WindEurope industrial conference in Bilbao Spain. Each work package leader, supported by work package researchers, detailed the progress of their technical work, highlighting the technical challenges they face, the solutions they proposed and gave an overview of their final steps on the project as well as their next steps after this EU project is complete. Feedback was provided on the day through numerous conference attendees dropping in and out of the XROTOR session. Additionally, feedback was obtained from GE during the meeting and after the meeting through the GE lead at Technical Management Meetings (TMTs).

4.2 Annual Meeting 3 Agenda

Time	Topic	Who
11.00	Welcome and Overview of Concept	UoS / BL
12.30	Non-Specialist Achievements from each WP	UoS, TU Delft, CENER, UCC and NTNU
13.30	Lunch	
13.45	Non-Specialist Achievements from full Project	UoS / BL
14.00	XROTOR Next Steps	UoS / JC
15.15	Break	
15.30	Researcher deep dive on each WP	UoS, TU Delft, CENER, UCC and NTNU
16.30	Poster technical sessions with refreshments	UoS, TU Delft, CENER, UCC and NTNU

4.3 Annual Meeting 3 Participants

In person	
Jordi Jove-Bellot	GE
Bill Leithead	UoS
James Carroll	UoS
Laurie Morgan	UoS
Jack Williamson	UoS
Reza Yazdanpanah	UoS
Seyed Mortazavizadeh	UoS
Luis Recalde Camacho	UoS
Simon Watson	TU Delft
Carlos Simao Ferreira	TU Delft
Beatriz Mendez Lopez	CENER
David Bensason	TU Delft
Michael Muskulus	NTNU
Adriana Correia da Silva	NTNU
Niall Dunphy	UCC
Peter Deeney	UCC

Online	
Abbas Mehrad Kazemi Amiri	UoS
David Campos Genoa	UoS
Fiona Devoy-McAuliffe	University College Cork

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this deliverable has provided an overview of the annual XROTOR workshops, which served as platforms for industry collaboration and feedback within the project. Through a series of three meetings held over the course of the project timeline, stakeholders from each institution have come together to share progress updates, tackle technical challenges, and chart future trajectories based on input from industrial stakeholders.

The workshops, hosted in various locations and supplemented with virtual participation, have facilitated robust discussions among work package leaders, researchers, and industrial partners, notably General Electric (GE). Each meeting's agenda, outlined with topics, timings, and designated speakers, ensured efficient dissemination of information and solicitation of feedback across all project areas.

Notably, the active engagement of GE representatives, both during and post-workshop, has been critical to the project's development by providing invaluable insights, critiques, and suggestions. This feedback, though not directly documented within this deliverable, has been instrumental in shaping the project's outputs and aligning them with industry requirements.

The holding of the workshops at venues such as the GE Offices in Barcelona and the WindEurope industrial conference in Bilbao, ensured the workshops served their intended purpose of gaining industrial feedback on the project work.